

Master in Sound and Music Computing
Universitat Pompeu Fabra

Transfer learning for automatic ABRSM grade evaluation

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Supervisor: Rafael Ramírez-Melendez

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Abstract

This thesis explores the use of transfer learning for Automatic Performance Assessment, a research area that aims to develop software applications that can analyse and grade musical performances. Such applications can assist students in their learning process, especially in their daily practice. However, current Automatic Performance Assessment applications are not reliable and effective enough for professional music education.

A dataset of karaoke performances was created, consisting of Amazing Grace recordings from Smule’s “Digital Archive of Mobile Performances”. The recordings were graded across the criteria of Pitch, Time, Tone, Shape and Performance, following the ABRSM grading guidelines. Hand-crafted features were extracted using Essentia, pYIN, DTW and vector distance measures as a baseline for performance evaluation. Features were also extracted from a music-tagging CNN and two audio compression VAE models: one trained on the same dataset and one trained on a different dataset. Linear kernel SVM classifiers were trained using these features and their test ROC AUC metrics were compared.

It was found that hand-crafted features performed better than NN-based features for Pitch, Time and Performance criteria, while NN-based features performed better than hand-crafted features for Tone and Shape criteria. The results suggest that transfer learning may be beneficial for some aspects of performance assessment.

Keywords: Automatic Performance Assessment; Music Information Retrieval; Feature extraction; Transfer Learning

Chapter 1

Introduction

1.1 Motivation

The goal of Automatic Performance Assessment is to create software applications that can evaluate and score musical performances. Automatic Performance Assessment can be a useful tool for students who want to improve their musical skills through feedback and guidance, especially during their daily practice sessions.

In this thesis, we try to automatically emulate marking criteria created by ABRSM, which stands for Associated Board of the Royal Schools of Music. ABRSM is a UK-based charity and examination board that conducts over 650000 music exams and assessments every year in 93 countries. ABRSM exams cover different aspects of a performance, such as accuracy, expression, and technique, and provide a rich and realistic assessment criterion for real-world automatic performance assessment.

Most of the existing research on Automatic Performance Assessment focuses on a single specific aspect of performance assessment, usually intonation or rhythm. In contrast, this thesis compares the performance of different algorithms for different marking criteria.

Automatic Performance Assessment is a challenging task that has not been fully solved yet. Therefore, we created a dataset that is easy to work with, but has some limitations: it contains only one song, and all recordings are made with the same backing track.

The recordings we use come from Smule’s “Digital Archive of Mobile Performances”. Smule is an American music app with a focus on solo and collaborative musical performances. The company has released several datasets under the name “Digital Archive of Mobile Performances”, which differ in the set of songs, performers and musical instruments.

This thesis explores the use of transfer learning for Automatic Performance Assessment. To the best of our knowledge, transfer learning technique, which has shown its effectiveness in other MIR tasks, has not been applied to this task yet. In the case of automatic performance assessment, transfer learning would imply using models that can assess some parameters and/or instruments well to improve the predictions for other parameters and/or instruments.

1.2 Objectives

The initial aim of this thesis was to develop an automated scoring system that emulates the ABRSM grading criteria using methods from Digital Signal Processing, Music Information Retrieval and Machine Learning.

However, during the literature review phase, it was discovered that there appeared to be a lack of research into the application of Transfer learning to Automatic Performance Assessment tasks. The focus has therefore shifted in this direction.

Finally, the ABRSM grading criteria provide a fairly diverse set of performance assessment criteria. One of the aims is to see the difference between the criteria from an automated assessment point of view. To do this, we compare the performance of several popular publicly available algorithms across all the assessment criteria.

1.3 Structure of the Report

The rest of this work is organised as follows:

- The state of the Art is reviewed in Chapter 2.
- Dataset creation process, together with a brief data analysis, is documented in Chapter 3, while the ABRSM marking criteria are set out in Appendix A.
- General algorithms evaluation principles are described at the beginning of Chapter 4. Sections 4.1 - 4.6 introduce the feature extraction algorithms, describe any modifications made, and provide relevant links and references.
- Sections 5.1 - 5.5 are devoted to detailed performance report of individual algorithms. Algorithms comparison is made in Section 5.6.
- The limitations of the methods and the analysis of the results are discussed in Section 6.1. The final conclusions are presented in Section 6.2.

Chapter 2

State of the Art

Music performance analysis is a research field that combines different disciplines, such as music information retrieval, empirical musicology, music perception, music education, and computational creativity [1, 2, 3]. Although not a substitute for a music teacher, software applications that analyse musical performances can help students in their learning process, especially in their daily practice. However, these applications are not yet reliable and effective enough to meet the high standards of professional music education [3].

In this thesis, we mainly focus on the technologies that can assess the playing skills of students from their audio recordings. We review the relevant literature on this topic in the following sections.

2.1 Performance Assessment Criteria

The parameters used to assess musical performance are often subjective and ill-defined, resulting in inconsistent opinions among music educators [4, 5]. Therefore, it is essential to identify the goals and purposes of the assessments [6, 7], and to design an appropriate assessment strategy accordingly. Depending on whether the assessments are intended to measure competence or to enhance learning, and whether they are focused on improvement or accountability, they can be classified as assessment

of learning (Summative) or assessment *for* learning (Formative) [8, 9, 10].

Performance parameters being evaluated typically relate to the accuracy of pitch and timing [11, 12, 13, 14], or the quality of sound (timbre) [15, 16, 17]. The selection of parameters for building an assessment tool may depend on the performer's proficiency level. For example, low-level parameters such as pitch or rhythmic accuracy may provide more useful feedback for beginners than higher-level parameters such as articulation or expression [1]. Additionally, the culture or the musical style may also affect the suitability of specific assessment parameters [18, 19].

Measurement tools can include checklists, rating scales, and rubrics [20, 21], which differ in their degree of objectivity and formative potential [6, 10, 9]. Checklists are simple yes/no lists of criteria that are suitable for summative assessments but not very informative for improvement. Rating scales indicate degrees of proficiency that are useful for both summative and formative assessments, especially with comments. Rubrics have criteria and performance-level descriptions that make them more objective and formative than the other tools. Rubrics can be general or task-specific, and holistic or analytic, depending on the purpose and context of the assessment.

2.2 Datasets, Instruments and Traditions

The existing literature on automatic performance assessment is quite limited in terms of genres and musical traditions: it focuses mainly on Western classical and Western popular music. There are, however, a few papers focusing on Jazz [22], traditional Georgian music [23], and Beijing Opera [24]. This may be due to the difficulty of the task and the lack of solutions even for the well-studied Western Music, let alone other musical traditions.

Most research is conducted on automatic assessment of Piano [2, 25, 26, 27, 28, 29], Singing Voice [30, 31, 32, 33, 34, 35, 36], and String Instruments [37, 38, 39, 40, 41, 42]. Other papers focus on Guitar [43, 3, 44, 45], Drums/Percussion [46, 47, 48, 49], Bamboo Flute [50], Bass [51], and Wind Instruments [22]. The list of publicly available datasets is presented in four tables divided by the instrument: Classical

Piano Datasets in Table 1, Singing Voice Datasets in Table 2, String Instruments Datasets in Table 3, Other Music Performance Datasets in Table 4.

Unfortunately, datasets for automatic performance assessment are still small, biased, genre specific and sometimes not openly available. Moreover, data used in the current state of the art papers tend to be domain specific (e.g. genre, level of difficulty), leading to biased machine learning models [2].

name	data	size	perf. params
APL [52]	audio	621 recordings	piano practice
ATEPP [53]	Audio, MIDI	1000 hours	timing, dynamics
CrestMusePEDB [54]	XML	121 performances	timing, dynamics
Duet [55]	MIDI	105 performances	timing, dynamics
JKU-ScoFo [56]	audio, MIDI	16 performances	timing, dynamics
Maestro [57]	audio, MIDI	200 hours	timing, dynamics
Mazurka [58]	beat markers	2732 recordings	tempo, dynamics
PGD [59]	audio, video, MIDI	210 recordings	gestures, intentions
SMD [60]	audio, MIDI	50 performances	timing, dynamics
SUPRA [61]	piano rolls, MIDI	478 performances	gestures, timing, dynamics
Vienna 4x22 [62]	audio, MIDI	4 pieces, 22 pianists	timing, dynamics

Table 1: Classical Piano Performance Datasets

name	data	size	perf. params
CSD [63]	audio, f0 series	48 recordings	intonation
DAMP	audio	24874 recordings, 14 songs	singing
Erkomaishvili [23] (<i>Georgian</i>)	audio, f0 series, MusicXML	116 recordings	timing, pitch
Intonation [64]	audio, f0 series	4702 performances	singing
Jingju-Pitch [24] (<i>Beijing Opera</i>)	f0 series	13MB	intonation
Karalk [65]	audio	1000 songs	singing
MASTmelody [32]	f0 series	1018 recordings	pass/fail ratings
VocalSet [66]	audio	6GB	singing techniques

Table 2: Singing Voice Performance Datasets

2.3 Assessment Methods

Music assessment systems can be categorised based on several major factors. One of them is the granularity of the assessment: some systems give note-by-note feedback [16, 34], while others evaluate the whole performance and give a single score [70, 13, 71]. Another factor is the use of score-based features, obtained by aligning the

name	data	size	perf. params
EEP [67] (<i>String Quartet</i>)	audio	23 recordings	timing, gestures, bowing techniques
QUARTET [42] (<i>String Quartet</i>)	audio, video	96 recordings	timing, gestures, bowing techniques
VGD [59] (<i>Violin</i>)	audio, EMG, IMU	960 recordings	position data, play- ing techniques
ViolinEtudes [37] (<i>Violin</i>)	audio, f0 series	27.8-hours	intonation

Table 3: String Instruments Performance Datasets

name	data	size	perf. params
CBFdataset [50] (<i>Bamboo Flute</i>)	audio	1GB	playing techniques
DrumPT [47] (<i>Drums</i>)	audio	30 recordings	playing techniques
Groove MIDI [48] (<i>Drums</i>)	MIDI	13.6 hours	drum timing
GPT [44] (<i>Guitar</i>)	audio	6580 recordings	playing techniques
IDMT-SMT-Bass [51] (<i>Bass</i>)	audio	3.6 hours	playing techniques
IDMT-SMT-Guitar [45] (<i>Guitar</i>)	audio	4700 note events	playing techniques
MASTrhythm [68] (<i>Percussion</i>)	audio	3721 recordings	pass/fail ratings
URMP [69] (<i>Multi Instrument</i>)	audio, video	44 pieces	timing, dynamics
WJazzD [22] (<i>Wind Instruments</i>)	MIDI	456 solos	timing, pitch

Table 4: Other Music Performance Datasets

audio to the score [12]. This approach was shown to be superior to score-independent methods for both hand-crafted features [72] and deep learning models [73].

A third factor is the modality of the assessment: some systems use multimodal data, such as video or motion sensors, to assess the technique (posture) of the performer [39, 40, 41], while the majority focus on audio or MIDI data obtained from the recording.

Many assessment scenarios measure similarity to a reference, drawing on the extensive literature on melodic similarity in Music Information Retrieval (MIR). This approach implies a step of performance transcription prior to the similarity estimation [74]. For more details, we refer the reader to the existing reviews [75] and

comparative studies [76] on melodic similarity. In general, distance metrics based on Dynamic Time Warping (DTW) are superior to other similarity measures [77].

Performance assessment tools have been created using different methods, but the common approach has been to extract descriptive features from the audio recording of a performance and use a classifier to predict the assessment [1]. This approach requires performance data (recordings) and human (expert) assessments for all the performance parameters being assessed. The classifiers in such systems are not very sophisticated, so the feature choice was a crucial part of the system design [15, 70, 78, 16, 79]. Several studies also attempted to incorporate information from the musical score or reference performance recordings into the feature computation process [80, 81, 12, 32, 36, 68].

However, recent methods have adopted advanced machine learning techniques such as sparse coding [82, 83] and deep learning [13]. These techniques do not rely on hand-crafted features that are musically important, but instead, input raw data (usually pitch contours or spectrograms) and train the models to automatically learn meaningful features that can accurately predict the assessment ratings. The common input representations for these machine learning models are Mel-Frequency Cepstral Coefficients (MFCC), fundamental frequency (f_0), Constant-Q Transform (CQT), pitch by YIN [84] or pYIN [85], and features generated by Deep Neural Networks (DNN) [2].

Various classical machine learning approaches have been used for automatic performance assessment, such as using weakly labelled data and unlabeled data [86], active learning [2], and contrastive learning [87]. However, transfer learning techniques, which have shown their effectiveness in other MIR tasks [88], has not been applied to this task yet. In the case of automatic performance assessment, transfer learning would imply using models that can assess some parameters and/or instruments well to improve the predictions for other parameters and/or instruments. This could be a promising direction for future research.

Chapter 3

Materials

3.1 Smule Digital Archive

Smule is an American music app with a focus on solo and collaborative musical performances. The company has released several datasets under the name “Digital Archive of Mobile Performances”, which differ in the set of songs, performers and musical instruments. Current work utilises karaoke recordings from the “Digital Archive of Mobile Performances – Smule – Amazing Grace”¹ (DAMP-S-AG).

The DAMP-S-AG contains 17582 solo singing performances from 17576 different singers on one and the same backing track – Amazing Grace. This is a real-world dataset from performances on the Smule karaoke app, containing mobile-device recordings of singers varying in age, gender, and geographic location. This allows to cross-compare vocal performances on the same backing track.

It is worth noting that the DAMP-S-AG also includes a backing track and a MIDI score. The score includes the vocal part and is perfectly aligned with the actual backing track, allowing for the calculation of score-dependent features. In addition, the dataset has rich metadata for each recording such as `account_id`, `country`, `city_id`, `gender`, `birth_year`, `creation_timestamp`, `device_os`, `headphones`, etc.

¹<https://zenodo.org/record/3596940>

3.2 Preprocessing

In order to create our own dataset from DAMP-S-AG we follow the next steps:

1. Select only those recordings that were created using headphones to prevent sound leaking. This step can be done using DAMP-S-AG’s metadata file “amazing_grace.tsv”. Essentially, this gives us monophonic voice recordings.
2. Cut a timeframe from 8s to 46s (38 seconds). It consists of several complete musical phrases. This step is mainly needed to speed up the grading process.
3. Normalise the loudness of the audio fragments to -20dBFS.
4. Keep the first 100 fragments for further grading and the last 900 fragments for unsupervised pretraining. This prevents our training and evaluation pipelines from data leaking.

Thus, all recordings intended for further grading and/or model training/evaluation undergo the same preprocessing steps.

3.3 Grading

During the dataset collection stage, a professional music teacher was asked to grade the prepared karaoke fragments according to the ABRSM marking criteria.

For each recording and each of the criteria (Pitch, Time, Tone, Shape, Performance) the music teacher gives a score from 10 to 30, with 20 being a pass mark. Full marking instructions are provided in Appendix A.

3.4 Analysis

As mentioned in Section 3.2, the dataset consists of the labelled part used to evaluate performance assessment algorithms and the unlabelled part used for unsupervised NN pretraining. The unlabelled part consists of 900 recordings.

Out of 100 recordings prepared for assessment, 49 were actually graded. Hence, the size of the labelled part is 49. Table 5 shows the distribution statistics for the different assessment criteria, while Figure 1 shows the distributions themselves.

	Pitch	Time	Tone	Shape	Performance
mean	20.53	22.32	20.20	20.87	20.95
std	5.09	4.19	5.02	5.10	5.21
min	10	10	10	10	10
25%	19	20	19	20	20
50%	21	24	20	20	20
75%	24	25	23	25	25
max	28	28	28	29	29

Table 5: ABRSM criteria distribution statistics.

Figure 1: ABRSM criteria distributions.

Chapter 4

Feature extraction

Since the labelled part of our dataset is small (49 audio fragments), we have to use transfer learning, algorithms that do not require training, or unsupervised pre-training on the unlabelled part of the dataset. For each recording, such approaches produce one or several numbers called features. After choosing a set of features (possibly coming from different algorithms), we evaluate their usefulness for predicting each assessment criterion by training a simple ML model on a given set of features.

Specifically, we predict the binary pass/fail rating (score ≥ 20 vs. score < 20) for each individual criterion using a linear kernel SVM classifier in order to mitigate overfitting. The classes are not perfectly balanced, so we use appropriate metrics: Precision, Recall, F1-score, ROC AUC. The 3-fold cross-validation is used, resulting in each metric having 3 values. We therefore report the mean \pm std of these values for both train and test sets. The test ROC AUC metric is chosen as the main metric and is used to compare different algorithms.

The current chapter is dedicated to the description of all the feature extraction methods used in this thesis. The selection of the feature sets for the final evaluation and comparison is done in Chapter 5. All the features from Sections 4.2, 4.3, 4.4 are score-dependent. They are obtained by comparing a given recording with the “ideal recording” synthesised directly from the MIDI score using MuseScore 4.

4.1 Essentia features

Essentia is an open-source library and tool for audio and music analysis, description and synthesis. For feature extraction, we have used the Essentia Music Extractor¹, which offers a wide range of features to choose from.

Several features listed below are based on the Harmonic Pitch Class Profile (HPCP)² from the spectral peaks of a signal. The HPCP is a $k \times 12$ dimensional vector which represents the intensities of the twelve ($k=1$) semitone pitch classes (corresponding to notes from A to G#), or subdivisions of these ($k>1$).

After initial experiments, we have identified and kept the following six features with the highest usefulness for ABRSM marking criteria prediction:

1. **tonal.tuning_nontempered_energy_ratio**³ — The ratio between the energy on non-tempered bins and the total energy, computed from the HPCP average.
2. **tonal.hpcp_entropy.mean**⁴ — Shannon entropy of an HPCP vector. Entropy can be used to quantify the peakiness of a distribution.
3. **tonal.key_krumhansl.strength**⁵ — This algorithm computes key estimate given a pitch class profile (HPCP). 'Krumhansl' - reference key profiles after cognitive experiments with users (should work generally fine for pop music). The strength of the estimated key is used as a feature.
4. **lowlevel.dynamic_complexity**⁶ — The dynamic complexity defined as the average absolute deviation from the global loudness level estimate on the dB scale. It is related to the dynamic range and to the amount of fluctuation in loudness present in a recording. Silence at the beginning and at the end of a track are ignored in the computation in order not to deteriorate the results.

¹https://essentia.upf.edu/streaming_extractor_music.html

²https://essentia.upf.edu/reference/streaming_HPCP.html

³https://essentia.upf.edu/reference/streaming_HighResolutionFeatures.html

⁴https://essentia.upf.edu/reference/streaming_Entropy.html

⁵https://essentia.upf.edu/reference/streaming_Key.html

⁶https://essentia.upf.edu/reference/streaming_DynamicComplexity.html

5. **lowlevel.dissonance.mean**⁷ — The sensory dissonance of an audio signal given its spectral peaks. Sensory dissonance (to be distinguished from musical or theoretical dissonance) measures perceptual roughness of the sound and is based on the roughness of its spectral peaks. Given the spectral peaks, the algorithm estimates total dissonance by summing up the normalized dissonance values for each pair of peaks.
6. **lowlevel.spectral_skewness.mean**⁸ — Skewness is a measure of the asymmetry of the probability distribution. Formally, spectral skewness is defined as the third standardized moment of the spectral shape.

4.2 pYIN & DTW

pYIN [85] is a modification of the YIN algorithm for monophonic fundamental frequency estimation. In the first step of pYIN, f0 candidates and their probabilities are computed using the YIN algorithm. In the second step, Viterbi decoding is used to estimate the most likely f0 sequence and voicing flags. See pYIN pitch contours for two randomly selected recordings vs. the “ideal recording” (white) in Figure 2.

Figure 2: pYIN pitch contours for two recordings vs. “ideal recording”.

⁷https://essentia.upf.edu/reference/streaming_Dissonance.html

⁸https://essentia.upf.edu/reference/streaming_CentralMoments.html

pYIN algorithm outputs pairs (t, p) meaning that for a moment t (s) a pitch value was estimated to be p (Hz). Formally, for two recordings this gives us sequences $t_1, p_1 : \{1, \dots, N_1\} \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$ and $t_2, p_2 : \{1, \dots, N_2\} \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$

The goal of the Dynamic Time Warping (DTW) algorithm is to align two sequences (in our case, p_1 and p_2) by minimising the distance between the aligned terms. It produces a path of length M : $(i, j) : \{1, \dots, M\} \rightarrow \{1, \dots, N_1\} \times \{1, \dots, N_2\}$, which satisfies the following two conditions:

- (1) $i(1) = j(1) = 1, i(M) = N_1$ and $j(M) = N_2$
- (2) $(i(k+1) - i(k), j(k+1) - j(k)) \in \{(0, 1), (1, 0), (1, 1)\}$

The distance function we use for DTW alignment is “log_dist” defined by Eq. 4.1, where $\lfloor x \rfloor$ is the nearest integer to x . The reasons for this choice are: firstly, the logarithmic scale better reflects human sound perception; secondly, we do not want to differentiate sounds that are an octave apart.

$$\log_dist(a, b) = \left| \log_2(a/b) - \lfloor \log_2(a/b) \rfloor \right| \quad (4.1)$$

The first feature we introduce is dtw_misalignment defined by Eq. 4.2, which quantifies the difference in timing between pitch-aligned recordings.

$$\text{dtw_misalignment} = \frac{1}{M} \sum_{k=1}^M \left| t_1(i(k)) - t_2(j(k)) \right| \quad (4.2)$$

The second feature we introduce is dtw_cost defined by Eq. 4.3, which quantifies the difference in pitch between pitch-aligned recordings.

$$\text{dtw_cost} = \frac{1}{M} \sum_{k=1}^M \log_dist(p_1(i(k)), p_2(j(k))) \quad (4.3)$$

To produce features utilised by our SVM classifier we use dtw_misalignment and dtw_cost between a given recording and the “ideal recording”.

4.3 Onset-based features

In order to create more features useful for predicting rhythmic accuracy, we reproduced the baseline assessment system described in [68]. The first step is to detect onsets, and then compare them with onsets from a reference recording. To make such a comparison, onsets are first time-quantified to produce onset vectors. These vectors are compared using rhythm-based (Beat Difference, Rhythmic Similarity), text-based (Jaro, Jaro-Winkler, Levenshtein, Damerau-Levenshtein) and vector-based (Hamming, Yule Similarity) methods.

Beat Difference is defined as the difference in the number of detected onsets, while Rhythmic Similarity distance is described in [89]. The remaining six similarity measures are well-known and hence we will not define them here. For onset detection, we use the OnsetDetection algorithm implemented by Essentia⁹. In particular, the High-Frequency Content detection (HFC)¹⁰ method was used with default parameters (sampling rate: 44100Hz, window size: 1024 samples, hop size: 512 samples).

For two sequences $t, v : \{1, \dots, M\} \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$ we define their time-quantised version $q[t, v, N] : \{1, \dots, N\} \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$ by Eq. 4.4. In the following, we will set the number of bins to $N = 500$, which gives us a bin of 76ms length. In the case of onset vectors, we will use the constant sequence $v = 1$, resulting in binary quantised vectors.

$$q[t, v, N](i) = \begin{cases} \max v(k), & \text{for such } k \text{ that } \frac{i-1}{N} \leq \frac{t(k)}{T} \leq \frac{i}{N} \\ 0, & \text{if there is no such } k \end{cases} \quad (4.4)$$

To produce features utilised by our SVM classifier, we use all eight distance measures described above between the time-quantised onset vectors for a given recording and the “ideal recording”.

⁹https://essentia.upf.edu/reference/streaming_OnsetDetection.html

¹⁰https://essentia.upf.edu/reference/streaming_HFC.html

4.4 Quantised pYIN vectors

Again, as in Section 4.2, we will work with the sequences $t_1, p_1 : \{1, \dots, N_1\} \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$ and $t_2, p_2 : \{1, \dots, N_2\} \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$ produced by the pYIN algorithm. Inspired by the methods of Section 4.3, we define a time-quantised pitch vector: for t, p we set $[p] = q[t, p, N = 500]$ defined by Eq. 4.4. In the following, we introduce features based on the difference between two time-quantised pitch vectors $[p_1], [p_2]$.

The first feature we introduce is `direct_deviation` defined by Eq. 4.5, which quantifies the difference in pitch between time-quantised pitch vectors.

$$\text{direct_deviation} = \mathbb{E} \left[\log_dist([p_1], [p_2]) \mid [p_1] \neq 0 \text{ and } [p_2] \neq 0 \right] \quad (4.5)$$

The second feature we introduce is `direct_mismatch` defined by Eq. 4.6, 4.7, which quantifies the difference in pitch and timing between time-quantised pitch vectors.

$$\mathbb{D}(a, b) = \begin{cases} 0, & \text{if } a = 0, b = 0 \\ 1, & \text{if } a = 0, b \neq 0 \text{ or } a \neq 0, b = 0 \\ 0, & \text{if } a \neq 0, b \neq 0 \text{ and } \log_dist(a, b) \leq 0.1 \\ 1, & \text{otherwise} \end{cases} \quad (4.6)$$

$$\text{direct_mismatch} = \frac{1}{N} \sum_{i=1}^N \mathbb{D}([p_1](i), [p_2](i)) \quad (4.7)$$

To produce features utilised by our SVM classifier we use `direct_deviation` and `direct_mismatch` between a given recording and the “ideal recording”.

4.5 ConvNet

As our first NN-based method, we used a pretrained music tagging CNN [88] to generate meaningful features for our task. In the original paper, this neural network was shown to be useful for a wide range of music classification tasks, so we decided

to use it as a baseline for other NN-based methods. The architecture is shown in Figure 3, and the pretrained weights are publicly available in a github repository¹¹.

Figure 3: ConvNet architecture suggested in the original paper.

However, we have slightly modified the feature extraction procedure. In [88], the authors aggregate feature maps from each of five layers using Average Pooling, obtaining vectors of $N = 32$ features. The resulting five vectors are then concatenated to produce the final feature vector. In our work, we experiment with different aggregation methods (Mean, Max, STD) and their combinations. In addition, we use features obtained from only a single layer to prevent our SVM classifier from overfitting.

4.6 VAE

Audio VAEs are able to embed audio fragments into low-dimensional latent space without significant loss of information, while at the same time preserving the meaningful structure of the latent space. This makes them ideal candidates for feature extraction algorithms. For this work, we decided to experiment with “RAVE: Real-time Audio Variational autoEncoder” [90], with publicly available source code¹².

¹¹https://github.com/keunwoochoi/transfer_learning_music

¹²<https://github.com/acids-ircam/RAVE>

In particular, we use two models:

(ExternalVAE) We use a model trained on 8h of Darbouka Recordings from an official internet archive¹³. The dimension of the latent space is 4.

(NativeVAE) The model trained from scratch on the unlabeled part of the dataset. It consists of 900 recordings totalling 9.5 hours, see Chapter 3 for more details. The architecture is identical to ExternalVAE, including the dimension of the latent space.

The receptive field of both models is approximately 600ms. We aggregate the latent representations (sampled at 21.5 Hz) over the time dimension using Mean, Max, STD and their combination. The general scheme is shown in Figure 4.

Figure 4: VAE internal state aggregation methods.

¹³https://acids-ircam.github.io/rave_models_download

Chapter 5

Results

5.1 Onset-based features

Evaluation of the onset-based features defined in Section 4.3 has shown that they were not able to beat random guessing, see details in Table 7. However, some of them have demonstrated marginally greater than zero correlation levels with assessment criteria as shown in Table 6.

Figure 5: Detected onsets with pYIN pitch contour and initial waveform.

	Pitch	Time	Tone	Shape	Performance
Beat Difference	0.04	0.05	-0.02	0.00	-0.08
Rhythmic Similarity	0.10	0.16	0.14	0.22	0.28
Jaro	-0.02	-0.06	0.03	0.00	0.08
Jaro-Winkler	0.19	0.05	0.18	0.14	0.21
Hamming	-0.12	-0.03	-0.05	-0.01	0.03
Levenshtein	-0.15	-0.12	-0.07	-0.15	-0.13
Damerau-Levenshtein	-0.15	-0.13	-0.07	-0.16	-0.15
Yule Similarity	-0.11	0.07	-0.08	0.01	0.00

Table 6: Pearson correlation coefficient for Onset-based features and different evaluation criteria on the labelled part of the dataset.

	Pitch	Time	Tone	Shape	Performance
Test Precision	0.34±0.01	0.40±0.01	0.35±0.02	0.38±0.00	0.39±0.01
Train Precision	0.54±0.25	0.40±0.01	0.54±0.24	0.57±0.25	0.40±0.01
Test Recall	0.43±0.10	0.50±0.00	0.43±0.10	0.45±0.07	0.47±0.04
Train Recall	0.57±0.09	0.50±0.00	0.54±0.05	0.58±0.12	0.49±0.01
Test F1-score	0.38±0.05	0.44±0.01	0.38±0.06	0.41±0.03	0.43±0.02
Train F1-score	0.52±0.15	0.44±0.00	0.49±0.09	0.56±0.17	0.44±0.01
Test ROC AUC	0.43±0.10	0.50±0.00	0.43±0.10	0.45±0.07	0.47±0.04
Train ROC AUC	0.57±0.09	0.50±0.00	0.54±0.05	0.58±0.12	0.49±0.01

Table 7: Final Onset-based features evaluation (linear SVM classification metrics).

5.2 CoreSet of handcrafted features

We combined all successful hand-crafted features in the so-called ‘‘Core Set’’. It includes all features from Sections 4.1, 4.2, 4.4. This feature set serves as a strong baseline for Transfer learning methods. Feature importance for each individual criteria is shown in Figures 6, 7, 8, 9, 10.

	Pitch	Time	Tone	Shape	Performance
Test Precision	0.93±0.10	0.62±0.13	0.92±0.09	0.87±0.07	0.88±0.07
Train Precision	0.93±0.05	0.98±0.00	0.91±0.05	0.91±0.05	0.91±0.06
Test Recall	0.93±0.10	0.79±0.23	0.88±0.09	0.84±0.09	0.84±0.09
Train Recall	0.93±0.05	0.81±0.04	0.88±0.04	0.88±0.02	0.86±0.06
Test F1-score	0.93±0.10	0.66±0.15	0.89±0.08	0.83±0.04	0.84±0.05
Train F1-score	0.93±0.05	0.87±0.03	0.89±0.04	0.89±0.03	0.88±0.05
Test ROC AUC	0.93±0.10	0.79±0.23	0.88±0.09	0.84±0.09	0.84±0.09
Train ROC AUC	0.93±0.05	0.81±0.04	0.88±0.04	0.88±0.02	0.86±0.06

Table 8: Final CoreSet features evaluation (linear SVM classification metrics).

Figure 6: CoreSet feature importance for Pitch criterion. Calculated as weights assigned to each feature by the linear SVM classifier (sklearn coef_ attribute).

Figure 7: CoreSet feature importance for Time criterion. Calculated as weights assigned to each feature by the linear SVM classifier (sklearn coef_ attribute).

Figure 8: CoreSet feature importance for Tone criterion. Calculated as weights assigned to each feature by the linear SVM classifier (sklearn coef_ attribute).

Figure 9: CoreSet feature importance for Shape criterion. Calculated as weights assigned to each feature by the linear SVM classifier (sklearn coef_ attribute).

Figure 10: CoreSet feature importance for Performance criterion. Calculated as weights assigned to each feature by the linear SVM classifier (sklearn coef_ attribute).

5.3 ConvNet-based features

First of all, we compared feature sets obtained from each individual layer of the network using all three aggregation methods simultaneously as shown in Table 9.

Layer Number	Pitch	Time	Tone	Shape	Performance
1	0.53±0.10	0.50±0.00	0.62±0.17	0.48±0.03	0.49±0.02
2	0.51±0.11	0.50±0.00	0.64±0.02	0.48±0.03	0.50±0.00
3	0.66±0.05	0.58±0.12	0.67±0.10	0.67±0.06	0.66±0.04
4	0.53±0.10	0.49±0.02	0.62±0.04	0.49±0.02	0.49±0.02
5	0.57±0.10	0.50±0.00	0.56±0.05	0.49±0.02	0.49±0.02
1, 2, 3, 4, 5	0.65±0.01	0.57±0.13	0.68±0.05	0.59±0.07	0.53±0.07

Table 9: Layerwise ConvNet features evaluation (linear SVM test ROC AUC).

Based on the evaluation metrics, it was decided to use only features obtained from the third layer. We compared different aggregation methods for the third layer features in Table 10. Finally, we decided to use all three aggregation methods simultaneously and did the final evaluation as shown in Table 11.

	Pitch	Time	Tone	Shape	Performance
Mean	0.50±0.00	0.50±0.00	0.50±0.00	0.50±0.00	0.50±0.00
Max	0.49±0.02	0.50±0.00	0.49±0.02	0.50±0.00	0.49±0.02
STD	0.50±0.00	0.50±0.00	0.50±0.00	0.50±0.00	0.50±0.00
Mean, Max	0.66±0.02	0.50±0.00	0.66±0.08	0.71±0.03	0.61±0.09
Mean, STD	0.56±0.14	0.49±0.02	0.52±0.08	0.56±0.14	0.58±0.12
Max, STD	0.53±0.10	0.50±0.00	0.56±0.12	0.50±0.00	0.50±0.00
Mean, Max, STD	0.66±0.05	0.58±0.12	0.67±0.10	0.67±0.06	0.66±0.04

Table 10: ConvNet feature aggregations evaluation (linear SVM test ROC AUC).

	Pitch	Time	Tone	Shape	Performance
Test Precision	0.75±0.14	0.64±0.24	0.76±0.16	0.67±0.06	0.69±0.02
Train Precision	0.98±0.00	0.98±0.01	0.97±0.01	0.97±0.01	0.96±0.01
Test Recall	0.66±0.05	0.58±0.12	0.67±0.10	0.67±0.06	0.66±0.04
Train Recall	0.91±0.01	0.75±0.07	0.86±0.04	0.82±0.06	0.78±0.06
Test F1-score	0.67±0.06	0.59±0.16	0.69±0.10	0.67±0.06	0.67±0.03
Train F1-score	0.94±0.00	0.82±0.06	0.90±0.03	0.87±0.05	0.83±0.05
Test ROC AUC	0.66±0.05	0.58±0.12	0.67±0.10	0.67±0.06	0.66±0.04
Train ROC AUC	0.91±0.01	0.75±0.07	0.86±0.04	0.82±0.06	0.78±0.06

Table 11: Final ConvNet-based features evaluation (linear SVM classification metrics).

5.4 VAE-based features

ExternalVAE

First of all, we compared different aggregation methods for the latent representations in Table 12. Finally, we decided to use all three aggregation methods simultaneously and did the final evaluation as shown in Table 13.

	Pitch	Time	Tone	Shape	Performance
Mean	0.64±0.10	0.50±0.00	0.61±0.08	0.50±0.00	0.50±0.00
Max	0.64±0.10	0.50±0.00	0.61±0.08	0.50±0.00	0.50±0.00
STD	0.50±0.00	0.50±0.00	0.50±0.00	0.50±0.00	0.50±0.00
Mean, Max	0.64±0.10	0.50±0.00	0.65±0.12	0.72±0.21	0.61±0.16
Mean, STD	0.72±0.21	0.50±0.00	0.65±0.14	0.56±0.08	0.64±0.10
Max, STD	0.72±0.21	0.50±0.00	0.65±0.14	0.56±0.08	0.64±0.10
Mean, Max, STD	0.71±0.21	0.50±0.00	0.71±0.15	0.81±0.14	0.75±0.07

Table 12: ExternalVAE feature aggregations evaluation (linear SVM test ROC AUC).

	Pitch	Time	Tone	Shape	Performance
Test Precision	0.70±0.24	0.46±0.01	0.72±0.23	0.97±0.03	0.96±0.01
Train Precision	0.96±0.03	0.81±0.24	0.97±0.01	0.97±0.01	0.96±0.01
Test Recall	0.71±0.21	0.50±0.00	0.71±0.15	0.81±0.14	0.75±0.07
Train Recall	0.79±0.17	0.67±0.14	0.83±0.07	0.82±0.06	0.75±0.04
Test F1-score	0.70±0.23	0.48±0.01	0.71±0.19	0.84±0.12	0.80±0.07
Train F1-score	0.82±0.17	0.70±0.17	0.88±0.06	0.87±0.05	0.81±0.04
Test ROC AUC	0.71±0.21	0.50±0.00	0.71±0.15	0.81±0.14	0.75±0.07
Train ROC AUC	0.79±0.17	0.67±0.14	0.83±0.07	0.82±0.06	0.75±0.04

Table 13: Final ExternalVAE-based features evaluation (linear SVM classification metrics).

NativeVAE

The model was trained on 900 unlabelled recordings totalling 9.5 hours. The training took 3.6h on Tesla V100, being interrupted after 35 epochs. Figure 11 suggests that the model did not fully converge. We compared different aggregation methods for the latent representations in Table 14. We decided to use all three aggregation methods simultaneously and did the final evaluation as shown in Table 15.

Figure 11: NativeVAE train and val loss on the unlabelled part of the dataset.

	Pitch	Time	Tone	Shape	Performance
Mean	0.50±0.00	0.50±0.00	0.56±0.08	0.50±0.00	0.50±0.00
Max	0.50±0.00	0.49±0.02	0.50±0.00	0.50±0.00	0.50±0.00
STD	0.50±0.00	0.50±0.00	0.46±0.05	0.50±0.00	0.50±0.00
Mean, Max	0.49±0.02	0.48±0.02	0.60±0.10	0.49±0.02	0.50±0.00
Mean, STD	0.53±0.07	0.49±0.02	0.63±0.12	0.65±0.24	0.60±0.17
Max, STD	0.59±0.09	0.50±0.00	0.61±0.11	0.70±0.05	0.53±0.07
Mean, Max, STD	0.80±0.14	0.49±0.02	0.92±0.09	0.88±0.15	0.75±0.19

Table 14: NativeVAE feature aggregations evaluation (linear SVM test ROC AUC).

	Pitch	Time	Tone	Shape	Performance
Test Precision	0.77±0.06	0.46±0.01	0.89±0.08	0.92±0.07	0.68±0.19
Train Precision	0.92±0.06	0.81±0.25	0.94±0.04	0.93±0.02	0.92±0.04
Test Recall	0.80±0.14	0.49±0.02	0.92±0.09	0.88±0.15	0.75±0.19
Train Recall	0.90±0.08	0.72±0.21	0.96±0.04	0.90±0.11	0.87±0.08
Test F1-score	0.77±0.10	0.47±0.01	0.90±0.08	0.87±0.12	0.71±0.19
Train F1-score	0.91±0.07	0.74±0.21	0.95±0.04	0.90±0.06	0.88±0.05
Test ROC AUC	0.80±0.14	0.49±0.02	0.92±0.09	0.88±0.15	0.75±0.19
Train ROC AUC	0.90±0.08	0.72±0.21	0.96±0.04	0.90±0.11	0.87±0.08

Table 15: Final NativeVAE-based features evaluation (linear SVM classification metrics).

5.5 CoreSet + NativeVAE-based features

Adding NativeVAE-based features to the CoreSet did not improve the metrics over the best of the two as can be seen in Table 16.

	Pitch	Time	Tone	Shape	Performance
Test Precision	0.88±0.09	0.46±0.01	0.86±0.10	0.92±0.06	0.91±0.08
Train Precision	0.94±0.05	0.80±0.25	0.93±0.05	0.91±0.05	0.91±0.06
Test Recall	0.92±0.09	0.50±0.00	0.86±0.10	0.85±0.09	0.79±0.03
Train Recall	0.95±0.05	0.64±0.10	0.90±0.07	0.88±0.02	0.86±0.06
Test F1-score	0.89±0.08	0.48±0.01	0.86±0.10	0.86±0.03	0.83±0.04
Train F1-score	0.94±0.05	0.68±0.15	0.91±0.05	0.89±0.03	0.88±0.05
Test ROC AUC	0.92±0.09	0.50±0.00	0.86±0.10	0.85±0.09	0.79±0.03
Train ROC AUC	0.95±0.05	0.64±0.10	0.90±0.07	0.88±0.02	0.86±0.06

Table 16: Final CoreSet + NativeVAE-based features evaluation (linear SVM classification metrics).

5.6 Algorithms comparison

Feature Set	Pitch	Time	Tone	Shape	Performance
Onset-based	0.43±0.10	0.50±0.00	0.43±0.10	0.45±0.07	0.47±0.04
CoreSet	0.93±0.10	0.79±0.23	0.88±0.09	0.84±0.09	0.84±0.09
ConvNet-based	0.66±0.05	0.58±0.12	0.67±0.10	0.67±0.06	0.66±0.04
ExternalVAE	0.71±0.21	0.50±0.00	0.71±0.15	0.81±0.14	0.75±0.07
NativeVAE	0.80±0.14	0.49±0.02	0.92±0.09	0.88±0.15	0.75±0.19
CoreSet + NativeVAE	0.92±0.09	0.50±0.00	0.86±0.10	0.85±0.09	0.79±0.03

Table 17: Final feature sets comparison (linear SVM test ROC AUC).

Final evaluation results for all considered feature sets are summarised in Table 17.

Based on the metrics we can see that:

- “Time” was the most difficult criterion to predict.
- Onset-based methods did not beat random guessing.
- The Core Set (see Section 5.2) of hand-crafted features outperforms all other methods for Pitch, Time and Performance criteria.
- The NN-based methods studied in this thesis were unable to predict Time criterion better than random guessing.
- ConvNet-based features perform significantly worse than VAE methods.
- VAE trained on the same distribution (NativeVAE) produce much better results than VAE trained on the other dataset (ExternalVAE).
- For Tone and Shape criteria NativeVAE outperforms CoreSet.
- Combining CoreSet with NativeVAE features does not improve results.

Chapter 6

Discussion

6.1 Discussion

The results have clearly demonstrated the potential usefulness of Transfer learning for Automatic Performance Assessment, which was the aim of the current work. However, it is important to understand that our methods have numerous limitations.

First of all, the labelled part of the dataset consists of only 49 recordings, which severely limits us in the choice of methods for comparison and prevents us from performing their comprehensive analysis. While some methods perform poorly on a small number of training examples, they may outperform all other methods on huge datasets, and vice versa. Furthermore, the statistical significance of many of the results is questionable and we cannot claim them with a high degree of certainty.

Secondly, as Automatic Performance Assessment is a difficult task that is not yet considered fully solved, we tried to create a dataset that would be easy to work with. This resulted in some restrictions: the dataset contains only one song, and all recordings are made with the same backing track. On the one hand, this allowed us to achieve a reasonable level of performance for most of the evaluation criteria. On the other hand, this raises the question of how well our results will generalise to more diverse datasets and cases closer to the real-world usage scenario.

Despite all the above, we will attempt to analyse the results, speculate on their reasons, and suggest further possible research directions.

The receptive field of all the NN-based methods we experimented with is not large enough to capture rhythmic patterns, while the aggregation methods used remove temporal information. It is therefore not surprising that these methods were unable to predict the Time criterion. However, we can hypothesise that some aspects are inherently more difficult for NN to predict than the others, and Time is one of them. Conversely, the Shape and Tone criteria may be the easiest to predict.

From the results of Section 5.6, we can see that ConvNet-based features perform significantly worse than VAE methods. Although this does not imply anything per se, it allows us to formulate the hypothesis that features obtained from audio compression models may have superior performance compared to features obtained from audio classification models. However, it might be the case that the SVM classifier is just severely overfitted because the feature space dimensionality is too high for ConvNet-based features.

The line of research that follows directly from the current work would be to experiment with more ways to aggregate internal NN representations, to try transfer learning methods that include the fine-tuning stage, and finally to try transfer learning for score-dependent NN architectures.

Furthermore, we have seen that VAE trained on the same distribution (NativeVAE) produce much better results than VAE trained on the other dataset (External VAE). It might be worth trying to quantify this effect for the transfer from one performance assessment dataset to the other.

Finally, it is interesting to investigate the reasons why onset-based features failed to beat random guessing on our dataset, even though they were effective in the other performance assessment tasks. Our results suggest that even classical MIR algorithms, which do not require any training, may be better suited to some datasets than others. It would therefore be important to measure the drop in performance of existing performance assessment algorithms as a result of changing the dataset.

6.2 Conclusions

In this work, we have successfully demonstrated the potential usefulness of transfer learning for Automatic Performance Assessment. To do this, a dataset of karaoke performances was created, graded across the criteria of Pitch, Time, Tone, Shape and Performance, following the ABRSM grading guidelines.

As a baseline for performance evaluation, we used several popular hand-crafted features utilising Essentia, pYIN, DTW and vector distance measures.

Against the baseline, we evaluated features obtained from a music-tagging CNN and two audio compression VAE models: trained on the same distribution and on a different dataset.

The results suggest that the features produced by these NN models can outperform the baseline solution for both the Tone and Shape marking criteria, despite the fact that the target on which they were trained is not similar to any of the ABRSM assessment criteria.

We therefore suggest that the use of transfer learning for Automatic Performance Assessment should be considered, as it may be beneficial in some situations. We also suggest that further research be carried out on this topic.

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Appendix A

ABRSM marking criteria

During the dataset collection stage, a professional music teacher was asked to grade the Amazing Grace karaoke recordings according to the ABRSM marking criteria. In particular, we followed the “ABRSM graded music exam marking criteria (Singing and Singing for Musical Theatre)”¹. A copy of the marking guidelines is provided below.

Performance grading principles

How do we mark exams?

ABRSM exams avoid the potential bias of instrument specialism by:

- applying universal, non-instrument-specific criteria
- focusing on the musical outcome, not the technical means behind it!

The marking criteria

The tables below show the marking criteria used by examiners in Singing exams.

¹<https://gb.abrsm.org/en/our-exams/information-and-regulations/graded-music-exam-marking-criteria-singing/>

Marking principles

In each element of the exam, ABRSM operates the principle of marking from the required pass mark positively or negatively, rather than awarding marks by deduction from the maximum or addition from zero.

In awarding marks, examiners balance the extent to which the qualities and skills listed below (broadly categorized by pitch, time, tone, shape and performance) are demonstrated and contribute towards the overall musical outcome.

Total marks

Practical graded music exams are marked out of a total of 150, with:

- 100 marks required for a Pass
- 120 marks required for a Merit
- 130 marks required for a Distinction

A Pass in each individual section of the exam is not required to pass overall.

Mark	Pitch	Time	Tone	Shape	Performance
Distinction 27–30	* Highly accurate notes and intonation	* Fluent, with flexibility where appropriate * Rhythmic character well conveyed	* Well projected * Sensitive use of tonal qualities	* Expressive, idiomatic musical shaping and detail	* Assured * Fully committed * Vivid communication of character and style
Merit 24–26	* Largely accurate notes and intonation	* Sustained, effective tempo * Good sense of rhythm	* Mainly controlled and consistent * Good tonal awareness	* Clear musical shaping, well-realised detail	* Positive * Carrying musical conviction * Character and style communicated
Pass 20–23	* Generally correct notes * Sufficiently reliable intonation to maintain tonality	* Suitable tempo * Generally stable pulse * Overall rhythmic accuracy	* Generally reliable * Adequate tonal awareness	* Some realisation of musical shape and/or detail	* Generally secure, prompt recovery from slips * Some musical involvement
Below Pass 17–19	* Frequent note errors * Insufficiently reliable intonation to maintain tonality	* Unsuitable and/or uncontrolled tempo * Irregular pulse * Inaccurate rhythm	* Uneven and/or unreliable * Inadequate tonal awareness	* Musical shape and detail insufficiently conveyed	* Insecure, inadequate recovery from slips * Insufficient musical involvement
13–16	* Largely inaccurate notes and/or intonation	* Erratic tempo and/or pulse	* Serious lack of tonal control	* Musical shape and detail largely unrealised	* Lacking continuity * No musical involvement
10–12	* Highly inaccurate notes and/or intonation	* Incoherent tempo and/or pulse	* No tonal control	* No shape or detail	* Unable to continue for more than a short section
0	* No work offered	* No work offered	* No work offered	* No work offered	* No work offered

Table 18: ABRSM marking criteria